

A309

21 JAN 94

Run P1 11:49:08–12:14:27 GMT

Run K1 12:15:15–12:17:16 GMT

Run K2 12:20:18–12:22:05 GMT

Run R1.1 12:23:28–12:28:29 GMT

Run R1.2 12:30:05–12:35:06 GMT

Run R1.3 12:36:44–12:41:44 GMT

Run R1.4 12:43:38–12:48:40 GMT

Run P2.1 12:42:00–12:44:36 GMT

Run R2.1 12:50:49–12:55:50 GMT

Run R2.2 12:57:19–13:02:20 GMT

Run R2.3 13:03:36–13:08:39 GMT

Run R2.4 13:10:09–13:15:10 GMT

Run R3.4 13:40:47–13:45:47 GMT

Run P2.3 13:46:16–13:50:12 GMT

Run R4 13:52:50–13:54:04 GMT

Run P2.4 13:54:04–13:57:19 GMT

Run P3 14:29:02-14:49:56 GMT

A309 21-JAN-94 Height time series

A309 21-JAN-94

FLIGHT FOLDER

DATE: 21 / 1 / 94 TAKE OFF 1001 H (local time) FLIGHT NO. A309
LANDING 1605

105-12

PROJECT OFFICER:
AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST: A. KAYE
FLIGHT LEADER: M. SMITH
OBSERVER: CLOUD PHYS: A. McHAFFIE
OTHERS:
FILTERS / CCN: D. LAUCHLAN
VACC: C. O'DOWD
~~PILOTS: D. ...~~

CAPTAIN: H. BURGOYNE
CO-PILOT: C. DALMEGE
NAVIGATOR: E. HEATON
ENGINEER: R. PRICE
LOADMASTER: K. QUICK

(A22) G. KNIGHT, S. ELVERY

TRIALS INSTRUCTION (s):
OPERATING AREA:

 W. OF IRELAND

GENERAL SYNOPTIC SITUATION:

A309 21st January, 1994

Start TIME (EM)	End TIME (EM)		HEIGHT	HDG
100108		Take off from FARNBOROUGH		
114908 (3)	-121427 (5)	Profile P1	FL200-> 70ft	270 deg
121515 (6)	-121716 (7)	K-GAMMA Run 1	100ft	270 deg
122018 (9)	-122205 (10)	K-GAMMA Run 2	100ft	090 deg
122328 (12)	-122829 (13)	Run 1.1	100ft	360 deg
123005 (14)	-123506 (15)	Run 1.2	100ft	170 deg
123644 (16)	-124144 (17)	Run 1.3	100ft	360 deg
124338 (18)	-124840 (19)	Run 1.4	100ft	170 deg
124200 (21)	-124436 (23)	Profile P2.1	100ft->1000ft	turning
125049 (21)	-125550 (22)	Run 2.1	1000ft	360 deg
125719 (23)	-130220 (24)	Run 2.2	1000ft	170 deg
130336 (25)	-130839 (26)	Run 2.3	1000ft	360 deg
131009 (27)	-131510 (31)	Run 2.4	1000ft	170 deg
131548 (32)	-132002 (33)	Profile P2.2	1000ft->3500ft	turning
132124 (34)	-132625 (35)	Run 3.1	3100ft	360 deg
132748 (36)	-133248 (37)	Run 3.2	3100ft	170 deg
133421 (38)	-133922 (39)	Run 3.3	3100ft	360 deg
134047 (40)	-134547 (42)	Run 3.4	3100ft	170 deg
134616 (43)	-135012 (44)	Profile P2.3	3100ft->5800ft	turning
135250 (46)	-135404 (47)	Run 4	5800ft	360 deg
135404 (47)	-135719 (48)	Profile P2.4	5800ft->7700ft	turning
135732 (49)	-140242 (51)	Run 5.1	7700ft	170 deg
140407 (52)	-140907 (53)	Run 5.2	7700ft	360 deg
141036 (54)	-141537 (55)	Run 5.3	7700ft	170 deg
141701 (56)	-142201 (57)	Run 5.2	7700ft	360 deg
142902 (58)	-144956 (63)	Profile P3	60ft->FL170	turning
160516		Land at FARNBOROUGH		

A309
21 January 1994
Aircraft Scientists summary

Synoptic Conditions:

It was decided to fly to the West of Ireland to study the Aerosol in the high wind region behind a series of frons which were approaching the British coast.

Flight Summary:

This flight was a succesful VACC flight with no major instrument problems effectively a duplicate of yesturdays flight.

SORTIE BRIEF: 21 JANUARY 1994

Variation of Aerosol Composition and Concentration VACC

- 1) SORTIE OBJECTIVE:** To determine the vertical structure of sea-salt and non-sea-salt sulphate aerosol in a clean marine boundary layer.
- 2) LOCATION:** Northeast Atlantic, 53-54N 11-20W. The sortie will be conducted directly up-wind of (and in the same air mass as) the Mace Head ground based research station.
- 3) WEATHER:** Non-precipitating, moderate to high wind region in the anti-cyclonic system edging northwards in the N. Atlantic. Air trajectory must be purely maritime. Forecast suggests polar maritime.

4) FLIGHT PATTERN:

- a. Transit over Ireland to sampling location and approx 20K ft (2hr 10min)
- b. Execute a profile to 50ft in cloud free air, if possible, @ 1000ft/min then, once in the marine boundary layer, profile @ 500ft/min (30min)
- c. Conduct a K-GAMMA wind field calibration (5min)
- d. VACC horizontal runs will be conducted at 100ft, 1,000ft and 2,000ft above sea-level (25min each) and in the free troposphere, but these altitudes may be changed slightly depending on marine boundary layer structure. Each VACC run will comprise two figure-of-eight race tracks across wind direction (total of four 5-minute legs, one for each heater tube, and an approximate one minute turn). Provision should be made for an extra run depending on layer structure. A short run through the broken cumuli cloud (500ft above CB) is required to determine cloud properties. In between VACC run profile at 500ft/min
- e. On completion of stack, terminate the scientific part of the flight with a profile down to 50ft @ 500ft/min (30min).
- f. Transit back to base (1hr 50min)

TOTAL DURATION Transit 4 hrs
 VACC 3-3.5hrs

Request diplomatic clearance to transit over Ireland

A309 21-JAN-94

GPS data
09:28:58 - 16:06:24

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: VACC Date: 20/1/94

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye

Flight No: A309 Page 1 of 5

GMT To: 10:00:08	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
10:08:15	00	TRANS	7.5 K	P	291	51.35	-1.42	Sc below confused above with Sc & Ci blue sky visible through gaps	
10:16:24	00	TRANS	15.5 K	P	290	51.48	-2.12	Sc below waves visible Sc above	
10:20:48	00	TRANS	19.1 K	P	290	51.57	-2.52	in cloud layer. see top!	
10:26:19	00	TRANS	19.9 K	P	284	51.68	-3.03	out of clouds hazy above, no sky visible 5/8 sc below some small gaps visible on right. Blue sea visible.	
10:35:23	00	TRANS	19.9 K	P	284	51.85	-4.13	5/8 cu below ^{clearing ahead} solid cloud above.	
10:56:00	00	TRANS	19.9 K	P	290	52.70	-6.06	7/8 sc below waves visible. thin ci just below 7/8 ci above.	
11:21:42	01	TRANS	19.9 K	P	284	53.50	-8.85	6/8 sc below occasional cu 7/8 ci above.	
11:34:55	02	TRANS	19.9 K	P	287	53.88	-10.20	4/8 sc/cu mixture 1/8 ci above.	
11:44:08	03	P1	200 R	P	289	54.25	-11.50	4/8 sc with some cu immediately below. thin ci above	
11:53:21	03	P1	15.3 K	P	291	54.35	-11.80	7/8 sc below just passed over edge thin ci above.	
12:00:32	03	P1	7.7 K	P	266	54.50	-12.29	approaching top of sc Deck.	
12:14:00	05	P1	7.0 K	K	253	54.44	-13.35	4/8 sc above hazy sea state 6.	

11:45

wind 40-30kts

CT.
7000
5200
4000

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kage.

Project: VACC

Date: 21/1/14

Flight No: A309

Page 2 of

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
						12:15:15	06		
12:20:18	09	K82	100ft	R	74	54.43	-13.54	end 12:22:05	
12:23:29	11	R1.2	100ft	R	346	54.45	-13.59	7/8 sc overhead.	
12:28:29	12	R1.1	100ft	R	342	54.73	-13.44	7/8 sc overhead.	
12:30:05	14	R1.2	100ft	R	154	54.70	-13.45	7/8 sc overhead Bright area directly ahead	
12:35:05	15	R1.2	100ft	R	152	54.47	-13.21		
12:36:44	16	R1.3	100ft	R	348	54.49	-13.26	7/8 sc above.	
12:41:44	17	R1.3	100ft	R	352	54.74	-13.29	7/8 sc above.	
12:43:37	18	R1.4	100ft	R	158	54.68	-13.29	8/8 sc overhead - bright area ahead.	
12:48:37	19	R1.4 / P2.1	100ft	R	155	54.45	-13.07	6/8 sc overhead.	
12:50:49	20	R2.1	1010ft	R	349	54.44	-13.10	8/8 sc overhead.	
12:55:50	21	R2.1	100ft		348	54.69	-13.14	Solid sc on overhead sea appears to be rougher at this end. shifting as we near calmer edge of sea slightly. Shear.	

1000:
4000
min
to 6

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. Kaye*

Project: *VACC* Date: *21/1/94*
 Flight No: *A309* Page *3* of

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
12:57:18	23	R2.2	1000	R	160	54.04	-13.14	Some light precip.	
13:02:18	22	R2.2	1000	R	159	54.42	-12.95	at edge of cc deck.	
13:03:46	23	R2.3	1000	R	B49				
13:08:37	24	R2.3	1000	R	346	54.68	-13.02.		
13:10:08	27	R2.4	1000	R	3157	54.63	-13.02	precip ahead the Sc deck appears to be breaking up to the south.	
13:15:08	31	R2.4	1000	R	170	54.42	-12.80		
13:15:44	32	R2.2	1000	P	303	54.40	-12.85	1/8 Sc. above some precip around.	
13:20:11	33	R2.2	3500	P	348	54.65	-12.86	Solid Sc above.	
13:21:24	34	R3.1	3100	P	347	54.69	-12.86	Just below Sc deck some light precip.	
13:26:25	35	R3.1	3100	P		54.86	-12.89	clear below Sc overhead.	
13:27:48	36	R3.2	3100	P	160	54.92	-12.71		
13:32:48	37	R3.2	3100	P	158	54.09	-12.69	5/8 Sc overhead.	

1430
 14:03
 1404
 11525
1555

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye.

Project: VACC Date: 21/1/84
Flight No: A309 Page 4 of

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
13:34:20	38	R3.3	3100	P	348	54.71	-12.74	hazy 8/8 sc above. Some gaps in sc as we fly to North.	
13:39:20	39	R3.3	3100	P	349	54.97	-12.74		
13:40:47	40	R3.4	3100	P	762	54.94	-12.76		
13:45:47	41	R3.4	3100	P	157	54.72	-12.54	7/8 sc overhead.	
13:46:16	43	P2.3	3100	P	211	54.68	-12.52		
13:50:30	45	R4	5400	P	348	54.89	-12.58	Just in and out of cloud. in thin level.	
13:52:50	46	R4	5800	P	3			in cloud.	
13:54:05	47	R4 P2.4	5800	P	345	55.07	-12.59	in cloud.	
14:15:37	55	R5.3 nd	7600	P	222	54.67	-11.99	thin ci above 8/8 sc below. VERY Sunny.	
14:17:01	56	R5.4	7700	P	348	54.70	-12.02	7/8 sc below.	
14:22:01	57	R5.4	7700	P	347	54.97	-11.98	thin ci overhead 8/8 sc below.	
14:29:53	58	P3	60 ft	R	216	54.74	-12.03	Sea State 5-6 1020 mb	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye

Project: VAcc Date: 21/1/94
 Flight No: A309 Page 5 of 5

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
						14:39:51	61		
14:45:23	61	P3	11.9K	P	123	54.09	-11.05	5/8 sc below thin ci overhead w/contrails.	
14:41:55	63	P3	16.5	P	124	53.92	-10.50	1/8 sc below thin ci overhead thickening to east.	
15:14:51	63	PA	24.8	P	129	52.79	-7.09	7/8 cloud below very confused sc/cu. Ci above ahead.	

BOOM OPERATORS LOG

FLIGHT A309 DATE 21/01/94 PROJECT VACC PART of

G.M.T.	HEIGHT	I.A.S.	RUN	FILTER	POS.N	PUMP	REMARKS
NB : BLANK TAKING IN BOOM AIR ON OUTWARD TRANSIT!							
105430	FL200	220	-	138	1/B	396.777	
105730	"	"	-	"	"	396.877	
122407	1100'	180	1	108	1/B	396.877	} FILTER SPLIT
134534						402.067	
NB Passed through precip several times							
135102	770'	180	5	116 116		402.067	
142202				116 116		403.396	
143340	-	-	-	120		403.396	BLANK
143550						403.545	

GMT	ALLEV.		Height	Dyn	STATIC							REMARKS
	On	Off			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
					1.0	2.5	5.0	3.5	4.25	5.0	5.5	
125100	✓		1000'	427	403	367	463	430	435	556	739	D
125200		✓		305	317	318	315	309	310	330	314	B Run 2
				2520	2475	2532	2532	2531	2527	2523	2521	R
					0.10	0.21	0.30	0.42	0.62	0.87	1.06	S
				2531								P
120346	✓		1000'	488	364	323	409	474	499	695	867	
120312		✓		301	300	305	304	321	305	323	310	Run 2
				2544	2522	2522	2527	2529	2535	2536	2536	
					0.10	0.21	0.30	0.41	0.62	0.86	1.06	
				976								
132130	✓		3100'	547	332	340	387	411	445	753	582	
132243		✓		294	299	313	300	293	293	298	296	Run 3
				2563	2599	2563	2564	2564	2564	2564	2564	
					0.10	0.21	0.30	0.41	0.61	0.86	1.05	
				905								
133425	✓		3100'	452	390	318	404	465	448	657	619	
133445				296	291	293	296	290	292	296	298	Run 3
				2585	2566	2562	2562	2564	2561	2562	2560	
					0.10	0.21	0.30	0.41	0.61	0.85	1.05	
				2564								
135734	✓		7700'		297	296	313	389	380	512	555	Run 5
135930		✓			295	296	293	296	299	298	315	
					2563	2564	2564	2564	2564	2557	2555	
					0.10	0.20	0.30	0.41	0.62	0.85	1.04	
141050	✓		7700'		293	300	339	360	316		502	
14125		✓			292	309	290	293	311		346	Run 5
					2546	2546	2545	2541	2541		2541	
					0.10	0.22	0.30	0.41	0.62		1.05	
14416	✓				301	332	297	427	460	685	628	D Cabin
144214		✓			318	303	300	300	302	318	303	B Plank
					2551	2550	2553	2547	2558	2549	2548	R
					0.10	0.21	0.30	0.42	0.62	0.87	1.07	S
					839							P

HDG deg T 289.	SPR mb 468.	PHGT kft 19.9	TAS knots 257.	TAT C -24.4	DEW C -23.5	WIND deg m/s 283/20
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ISE DP

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

HDG deg T 283.	SPR mb 467.	PHGT kft 19.9	TAS knots 279.	TAT C -24.6	DEW C -26.0	WIND deg m/s 284/19
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			WIDEO	HELP

2D-C CONC #/1

PCASP CONC	#/cc	21
PCASP MEAN RAD	u	0.22
PCASP MASS	ug/m3	17.61

FSSP CONC	#/cc	0
FSSP MEAN RAD	u	8.4
FSSP LWC	gm/m3	0.00

2D-C CONC	#/1	29.5
2D-C MAX SIZE	u	0
2D-C LWC	g/m3	0.000e+000

94-01-21 10:39:14

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
1000

1 0.1 10
1 0.1 10

A309 21-JAN-94 12:20:24 009 Q 54.42 -13.57 RV

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
74.	1016.	-0.1	181.	7.4	0.6	266/32

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

PCASP CONC/cc

500

PCASP CONC #/cc 176
 PCASP MEAN RAD u 0.13
 PCASP MASS ug/m3 4.36

FSSP CONC #/cc 0
 FSSP MEAN RAD u 2.3
 FSSP LWC gm/m3 0.00

2D-C CONC #/l 0.0
 2D-C MAX SIZE u 0
 2D-C LWC g/m3 0.000e+000

94-01-21 12:38:16

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
1000

1
1

0.1
0.1

10
10

A339

21 JAN 94

14:21:03

056 Ω

54.92 -11.99

FR P

HDG deg T 348.	SPR mb 767.	PHGT k ft 7.5	TAS knots 206.	TAT C -4.5	DEW C -28.9	WIND deg m/s 239/12
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GE DP

A SELECT	H PARAS	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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A309

21-JAN-94

14:46:12

061

54.05 -10.98

AS P

HDG degT 125.	SPR mb 624.	PHGT kft 12.8	TAS knots 223.	TAT C -10.2	DEW C -29.0	WIND deg m/s 253/35	
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A SELECT	B	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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A309

21-JAN-94

15:02:00

063

Ω

53.46

-8.96

RV

HDG	SPR	PKGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
degT	mb	kft	knots	C	C	deg m/s
128.	378.	24.9	303.	-36.0	-36.5	269/54

GE DP

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

FACIT 4-UP

12Z 21 JAN 1994

**STORNOWAY
03026
AT 11Z**

10		
15		
20		
25		
30		
40	255	142
50	255	121
60	265	112
70	270	65
85	265	50
100	250	21
MAX	NIL	
TROP	202	-61
10		
15	1328	
20	1148	
25	1007	
30	890	
40	695	
50	536	
60	285	
70	285	
85	136	
100	6	
10		
15	180.0	
15	141.0	
15	117.0	
15	195.0	
15	159.0	
15	251.0	
15	278.7	
15	129.9	
15	529.7	
10		
15	-62	
20	-61	

**VALENTIA
03953**

10	265	34
15	255	54
20	270	55
25	260	56
30	265	65
40	270	50
50	270	46
60	270	44
70	270	50
85	265	31
100	265	35
MAX	29776	
TROP	181	-70
10		
15	1605	
20	1197	
25	1048	
30	930	
40	732	
50	570	
60	311	
70	155	
85	21	
100		
10		
15	246.0	
15	172.0	
15	159.0	
15	118.0	
15	196.0	
15	162.0	
15	259.3	
15	289.6	
15	133.6	
15	548.9	
10		
15	-65	
20	-69	
20	-66	

**BOULMER
03240
AT 11Z**

10	260	35
15	270	76
20	265	75
25	260	66
30	265	60
40	265	55
50	260	52
60	265	44
70	270	53
85	265	48
100		
MAX	13399	
TROP	270	82
10		
15	1992	
20	1173	
25	1035	
30	917	
40	721	
50	560	
60	301	
70	144	
85	11	
100		
10		
15	249.0	
15	170.0	
15	138.0	
15	118.0	
15	196.0	
15	161.0	
15	259.3	
15	289.9	
15	133.5	
15	549.2	
10		
15	-69	
20	-67	
20	-68	

**LONG KESH
03920
AT 11Z**

10	275	46
15	260	66
20	260	61
25	255	76
30	265	72
40	260	69
50	265	66
60	265	60
70	265	59
85	275	15
100	275	18
MAX	11258	
TROP	178	-71
10		
15	1597	
20	1176	
25	1037	
30	919	
40	723	
50	561	
60	303	
70	142	
85	15	
100		
10		
15	249.0	
15	172.0	
15	159.0	
15	118.0	
15	196.0	
15	162.0	
15	258.1	
15	288.3	
15	132.9	
15	546.1	
10		
15	-66	
20	-68	
20	-67	

FACIT 4-UP

12Z 21 JAN 1994

21 JAN '94 13:32

MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_1 PAGE.001

FACIT 4-UP

12Z 21 JAN 1994

CAMBORNE
03808
AT 11Z

10	280	19
15	285	20
20	320	25
25	300	24
30	290	26
40	295	31
50	290	28
60	300	28
70	280	22
85	295	30
100	270	18

MAX T 200 95
TROP 167 -70
290 27

10	1607
15	1361
20	1189
25	1050
30	932
40	736
50	574
70	315
85	157
100	25

15	246.0
15	172.0
15	139.0
15	118.0
15	196.0
15	162.0
15	259.4
15	290.0
15	132.3
15	549.4

10	-66
15	-68
20	-66

HEMSBY
03496
AT 11Z

10	280	23
15	285	30
20	270	29
25	285	26
30	285	32
40	290	27
50	290	31
60	280	32
70	275	29
85	270	26
100	255	21

MAX NIL

TROP 148 -72
285 31

10	1600
15	1356
20	1183
25	1044
30	926
40	730
50	569
70	310
85	152
100	20

15	244.0
15	173.0
15	139.0
15	118.0
15	196.0
15	161.0
15	259.2
15	290.3
15	132.6
15	549.3

10	-68
15	-72
20	-64

HERSTMONCEUX
03882
AT 11Z

10	315	21
15	320	21
20	305	21
25	300	23
30	330	23
40	325	19
50	320	19
60	335	14
70	325	19
85	270	23
100	270	20

MAX NIL

TROP 144 -72
325 20

10	1605
15	1361
20	1188
25	1048
30	930
40	754
50	572
70	313
85	155
100	23

15	244.0
15	173.0
15	140.0
15	118.0
15	196.0
15	162.0
15	259.4
15	289.9
15	132.3
15	549.3

10	-67
15	-71
20	-63

AUGHTON
03322
AT 11Z

10	285	29
15	275	28
20	290	45
25	280	52
30	275	36
40	280	42
50	275	46
60	275	49
70	280	42
85	280	59
100	235	19

MAX NIL

TROP 173 -72
275 37

10	1602
15	1355
20	1184
25	1046
30	927
40	729
50	566
70	307
85	151
100	18

15	247.0
15	171.0
15	138.0
15	118.0
15	198.0
15	163.0
15	258.7
15	289.2
15	133.0
15	547.9

10	-66
15	-68
20	-66

21 JAN '94 13:34 FACIT 4-UP

12Z 21 JAN 1994

SMUK-IE EGRR
21 JAN 1994 AT 12Z

57.5N 23.6W
GFCR
02 099
35 057
027 10
093 08

GRJ
09 071
98 101
04 35

62122
08 127
07 07

62124
07 185
06 07

098 58182
70 051
09 192
054 20
196
07 07
052 15
10 051

6 7530
10 562182
80 011
062 22 7531
09 562195
81 011
052 15

07 185
06 071

PLAT
09 215
07 071

11 10 09
55
09 302
08 194
80 1087
067 54
09 214
70 1014
056 70
4 12

SMEW EGRR
21 JAN 1974 AT 12Z

DATA CUT-OFF TIME 12.41

Handwritten:
1013
1010
1007

HIGH

1033

LOW

53.5N08.5E 53.9N08.7E

05 228 08	06 193 14
04 04	05 04

54.7N10.0E 54.1N12.0E

06 186 14	05 213 12
05 04	04 05

21 JAN 1994 AT 12Z

UM/UJXX EGRR

12 Z

FRI

21

JAN

1994

RUN

1

VALENTIA
03953
10 -65
15 -69
20 -66
T 181 -70

100	265	35
	270	30
85	265	31
80	265	36
70	270	50
60	270	44
50	270	46
40	270	50
30	265	45
25	260	56
20	270	55
15	255	54
10	265	34
MAX	28776	
T	290	61

CAMBORNE
03808
AT 11Z
10 -66
15 -68
20 -66
T 167 -70

100	270	18
	285	24
85	295	30
80	275	28
70	280	22
60	300	28
50	290	28
40	295	31
30	290	26
25	300	24
20	320	25
15	285	28
10	280	19
MAX	NIL	

DE BILT
06260
10 -67
15 -72
20 -65
T 153 -73

100	230	21
	245	20
85	270	20
80	275	22
70	310	16
60	330	17
50	315	17
40	330	17
30	300	21
25	310	13
20	330	16
15	330	28
10	305	21
MAX	NIL	